

Robust Control for Microgravity Vibration Isolation With Parametric Uncertainty

Dr. Mark S. Whorton
TD55/Control Systems Group
NASA Marshall Space Flight Center
Huntsville, AL 35812

Abstract:

Many space-science experiments need an active isolation system to provide a sufficiently quiescent microgravity environment. Modern control methods provide the potential for both high-performance and robust stability in the presence of parametric uncertainties that are characteristic of microgravity vibration isolation systems. This paper compares microgravity vibration isolation control system designs using H_2 and H_∞ methods on the basis of nominal performance and robustness to parametric uncertainties.

1. Introduction

Earth-orbiting spacecraft provide the potential for conducting research in a low-level acceleration environment, enabling the investigation of phenomena otherwise masked by gravity on earth. The International Space Station (ISS) is envisioned as a research laboratory for unique state-of-the-art microgravity (μg) science investigations in disciplines such as life sciences, materials science, combustion, fundamental physics and fluid mechanics. However, due to a variety of vibro-acoustic disturbances on the ISS, the acceleration environment is expected to significantly exceed the requirements of many acceleration sensitive experiments. Figure 1 presents an estimate of the acceleration environment on the ISS at assembly complete, which exceeds the required acceleration levels for μg science (from the ISS Microgravity Environment Specification [1]) at virtually all frequencies.

FIGURE 1. Predicted RMS Acceleration Environment of the International Space Station

Mitigation of the excessive acceleration environment requires the implementation of vibration isolation systems at either the disturbance source or the science payload. While an effort is being made to limit the induced disturbances, it is understood that the acceleration levels will not meet the environment requirement specification, thus requiring the use of vibration isolation at the payload/rack locations. From the anticipated environment one may derive an attenuation function that would reduce the ambient environment sufficiently to provide the required environment at the payload location. The derived attenuation requirement reduces the anticipated ISS acceleration level to within the required ISS acceleration levels and is shown in Figure 4.

Three distinct frequency regions characterize the attenuation requirement. At frequencies below 0.01 Hz, the isolation system must directly transmit the very low frequency quasi-steady accelerations to prevent the isolated elements from bumping into the vehicle. The requirement for isolation from base motion implies that a "rattle-space" must exist around the isolated elements to allow them to remain stationary with respect to inertial space while the vehicle vibrates. Obviously, it is undesirable for the isolated elements to bump into the moving base since this not only negates the vibration isolation but also transmits an impulsive acceleration to the isolated element. Between 0.01 Hz and 10 Hz, the amount of attenuation must increase one order of magnitude for every decade of frequency. Three orders of magnitude attenuation is required above 10 Hz. Hence the isolation system must sense and cancel accelerations with a magnitude of one-millionth the acceleration of gravity at the surface of the earth ($1 \mu\text{g}$) occurring over tens of seconds. Additionally, some payloads require command tracking or cancellation of direct disturbance forces at frequencies of tens of Hz, thus necessitating high bandwidth control with the resulting potential for interaction between control and payload structural dynamics.

Applications of H_2 and H_∞ control abound in the literature, yet the application of robust control methods to microgravity vibration isolation has only been minimally addressed. Much like traditional flexible space structures, microgravity vibration isolation systems require high performance control of uncertain systems. The distinctions, however, lie in the range of frequencies, operational constraints, and levels of measurements to

which the control systems must be applied. While H_2 designs for microgravity vibration isolation systems have been published [3, 4], an analysis of robustness with respect to the parameter variations specific to this application has not been done. H_∞ methods have been applied to the Active Rack Isolation System to gain stabilize high frequency unmodeled modes [5]. Absent from the literature is a consideration of robustness and performance with respect to parametric uncertainty within the control bandwidth that is characteristic of microgravity vibration isolation systems. This paper advances the literature by comparing H_2 and H_∞ controllers from a perspective of both nominal performance and robust stability while also developing H_∞ controllers that provide robust performance for parametric uncertainties in the control bandwidth.

2. g-LIMIT System Description

g-LIMIT (GLovebox Integrated Microgravity Isolation Technology) is a microgravity vibration isolation system being designed and built by the NASA Marshall Space Flight Center to provide active vibration isolation for μg science payloads on the International Space Station [6]. Shown in Figure 2, g-LIMIT is scheduled for launch on the 11A mission in September 2002 and will commence characterization testing shortly thereafter. G-LIMIT is approximately 13 inches high, 15 inches long at the base and 14 inches wide at the base.

Figure 2. g-LIMIT System Assembly

There are two main subsystems of g-LIMIT: the inertially isolated assembly to which an experiment is mounted and the base assembly which is rigidly attached to the ISS rack support structure. Control forces are applied to the isolated assembly using non-contact Lorentz force actuators, each with a peak magnitude of approximately 3 N per axis. Inertial force-balanced proof mass accelerometers are used to measure the inertial motion of the isolated platform and a unique patent-pending relative position sensing system is used to measure the relative motion of the isolated assembly with

respect to the ISS-mounted base assembly. Three lock-down fasteners are used to secure the isolator assembly to the base plate during transport, stowage, installation and idle times. Integrated into the base assembly and the isolated assembly is a snubber system which provides mechanical rattle-space constraints with a maximum relative displacement of ten mm between the isolator assembly and the base assembly. g-LIMIT accomplishes inertial isolation using a high gain, high bandwidth acceleration feedback control system that applies six independent forces to the isolated platform upon which an acceleration sensitive experiment is mounted. An outer-loop (low frequency) position feedback controller is used to maintain centering of the isolated platform. One key objective of the on-orbit characterization test will be to evaluate the stability and robustness characteristics of numerous g-LIMIT control systems, including classical designs and the modern control design methods addressed in this report.

3. Control system design

Classical control methods are known to provide inherent robustness and simplicity of design and implementation. However, classical control methods are not well suited for multivariable (coupled) systems with parametric uncertainties. Such is the case with microgravity vibration isolation systems. Isolation systems cannot be tested in six degrees of freedom on the ground due to gravitational coupling, hence the dynamic properties of the system are often poorly known prior to on-orbit operation. The combination of poorly known payload mass properties, payload structural dynamics, and flexible umbilicals passing resources from the vehicle to the isolated platform results in a multivariable uncertain dynamic system.

For the control designs in this paper, the generalized plant of a multi-input, multi-output system may be written in state space form as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= A_p x + B_{1p} w + B_{2p} u \\ z &= C_{1p} x + D_{12p} u \\ y &= C_{2p} x + D_{21p} w + D_{22p} u \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $x \in \mathcal{R}^n$ is the state vector, $w \in \mathcal{R}^{nw}$ is the disturbance vector, $u \in \mathcal{R}^{nu}$ is the control vector, $z \in \mathcal{R}^{nz}$ is the performance vector, and $y \in \mathcal{R}^{ny}$ is the measurement vector. The H_2 (H_∞) optimization problem is to find a stabilizing controller that minimizes the H_2 (H_∞) norm of the closed loop system from disturbance inputs w to performance outputs z , denoted T_{zw} . With reference to Figure 3, the disturbance inputs include the three translational base accelerations, w_{acc} ; three directly applied forces, w_{fd} ; six elements of the accelerometer noise vector, n_{acc} ; and six elements of the position sensor

Figure 3: Block Diagram for Nominal Performance Control Design

noise vector, n_{pos} . The performance outputs include weighted control, z_u ; weighted platform acceleration, z_{acc} ; and weighted platform relative position, z_{pos} . The measurement vector consists of six platform accelerations, six relative positions, and the six actuator forces of the control input vector.

H_2 methods are often used when designing control systems to reduce the vibration response of a flexible structure. While H_2 design gives good nominal performance, the controllers are highly tuned to the design model and errors in the design model are not accounted for, typically inducing instability at higher levels of control authority. As a result, the actual performance achievable is limited with H_2 designs. To achieve high levels of performance in the presence of uncertainties associated with umbilical and payload (isolated experiment) dynamics, robustness to model errors must be taken into account in the design process.

Another approach to design for nominal performance employs the H_∞ norm, which can be interpreted as the gain of the system and is the worst-case amplification over all inputs $w(t)$ of unit energy. From a frequency domain perspective, the H_∞ norm is defined as the maximum singular value of $T(s)$ over all frequencies. Because the H_∞ norm is defined with respect to the peak magnitude of the transfer matrix frequency response and the H_2 norm is defined by an integral square quantity (in time or frequency by Parseval's Theorem), the respective closed loop systems typically have considerably different characteristics. Depending on the performance objectives, one design procedure may be preferable to the other. With regard to mean-square performance specifications such as microgravity vibration isolation, H_2 design is typically better suited for nominal performance.

The significant benefit of H_∞ theory however is that robustness to model errors is explicitly factored into the design process.

4. Uncertainty Modeling for Control Design and Analysis

A key objective of control system design is robustness to variations between the actual system and the model on which control designs are based. For microgravity vibration isolation systems, the primary uncertain parameters of interest are the payload mass, umbilical stiffness, umbilical damping, and composite isolation system/payload center of gravity (cg). Although both mass and stiffness or mass and damping uncertainties are important for consideration, it is evident that the mass terms appear in the system A matrix (from which stability is determined) as products with the stiffness and damping. Hence, both uncertainties cannot be considered simultaneously with standard linear robust control methods. Simultaneous mass and stiffness or mass and damping uncertainty need not be considered however since mass uncertainty may be effectively accounted for in either stiffness and damping uncertainty or uncertainty in the product term itself.

Considering only one uncertain umbilical and treating the uncertainties as additive parametric uncertainty, the uncertain umbilical stiffness and damping may be defined, respectively, as

$$K_u = (K_u)_0 + \Delta K_u$$

$$C_u = (C_u)_0 + \Delta C_u$$

where the "0" subscript indicates the nominal value. Each of the uncertain parameters is isolated in the equations as additive terms in the system A_p and B_{2p} matrices (the control coefficient matrix in the state equation) to derive a parametric uncertainty model for robust control design. For example, the system A_p matrix may be written as the nominal portion plus the uncertain contributions, or

$$A = A_0 + \Delta A_K + \Delta A_C + \Delta A_{cg}$$

where the nominal portion, A_0 , is the A_p matrix corresponding to zero uncertainty. The full development of the uncertainty model is presented in Reference 8. Uncertainties in the disturbance input are not included herein as they are treated directly in the weight selection for robust control design. This uncertainty model is used in this paper for analyzing the robust stability of the H_2 designs as well as designing for robust stability and performance designs using μ -synthesis methods [7].

5. Control system design

For the H_2 control designs, the control weight, ρ , ranged from 1 to 0.01 to vary control authority. Figure 4 shows the nominal performance design results for the H_2 control designs as the control authority is varied. Although the required isolation performance is met for $\rho = 0.01$, the output cost versus control cost plot in Figure 5 indicates that the performance requirement is met only at a high control cost. A much more desirable design point from the perspective of cost efficiency is at the elbow of the curve, although controllers in this region do not meet the performance requirement.

Figure 4: Closed Loop Transmissibility Maximum Singular Values for H_2 Designs

One would anticipate that the high control cost increase incurred for a small decrease in output cost implies poor stability robustness for the H_2 designs. This is in fact the case as evidenced by Figure 6, which shows the peak μ measure for each H_2 control design, with varying control authority, evaluated with respect to

parametric uncertainty ranging from 1.25% to 25%. Even for the lowest performance H_2 control designs, the peak μ values increase dramatically. A slice taken through the surface plot in Figure 6 at $\rho = 1$ is shown in Figure 7 to illustrate the effect on robust stability of parametric uncertainty for the lowest performance H_2 control design.

Figure 5: Closed Loop Cost Trade for H_2 Nominal Performance Designs

Figure 6: Peak μ Measure Values for H_2 Designs

Figure 7: Peak μ Measure Values as a Function of Parametric Uncertainty

Although the system is essentially a six-axis spring-mass-damper, very high gain acceleration feedback is required to achieve the attenuation performance requirement. With a mass of 16 kg for the isolated platform/payload assembly and an umbilical stiffness of 50 N/m, the passive (open-loop) natural frequency is 0.28 Hz. To achieve a closed loop natural frequency of 0.01 Hz would require a mass of 12,665 kg, so the acceleration feedback gain effectively makes the system 800 times more massive. High gain feedback is required to meet the attenuation requirement, but the resulting system is somewhat sensitive to parametric uncertainty.

As a point of comparison, a set of μ -synthesis controllers was designed for varying levels of parametric uncertainty. A nominal performance H_∞ design which met the attenuation performance requirement was used to determine the performance weights and serve as a basis for the robust performance designs. For the H -infinity design, the acceleration performance weight,

$$W_{paccel} = \frac{0.01 * \left(\frac{s}{.00075 * 2\pi} + 1 \right)}{\left(\frac{s}{10 * 2\pi} + 1 \right)}$$

which approximates the shape of the inverse of the attenuation requirement, is used so that a closed loop with an infinity norm less than one will satisfy the attenuation requirement. This weight effectively shapes the frequency response of the closed loop such that the penalty is low at low frequencies to maintain unity transmissibility and then increases to force the transmissibility to begin rolling off according to the attenuation requirement. For the H_∞ control, anti-aliasing filters are also included in the sensor measurements. All other weights in the optimization process are constants.

Figure 7 presents a comparison of the robust stability and robust performance μ values for the set of μ -synthesis designs with the robust stability μ values for the H_2 designs. As is well known, the H_2 designs are substantially more sensitive to parametric variation than are the μ -synthesis designs. Robust performance in the context of the μ -synthesis designs does not exactly correlate with the required attenuation performance for this application. The robust performance problem includes other inputs and outputs such as noise and position errors while the attenuation performance requirement is strictly defined as the transfer function from base acceleration to platform acceleration. However, in comparison to the H_2 designs, both robust stability and robust performance μ values are very low, in the range of 2 - 5, and are relatively insensitive to parametric uncertainty. The H_∞ nominal performance design satisfies the attenuation requirement as shown in Figure 8, which also shows the affect of parametric uncertainty on attenuation performance. Note that

whereas performance is exchanged for robustness with the μ designs, the H_2 designs do not provide robustness in exchange for loss in performance. In other words, the H_2 designs are non-robust, whether low or high performance designs.

Figure 8: Effect of Uncertainty on Attenuation Performance of μ Designs

Additional work is required to arrive at controllers that can be implemented in flight hardware. All control designs for this study are full order with the result that the H_2 controllers are 15th order and the μ controllers range from 102 states to 188 states. Aside from introducing numerical difficulties, there is no way that these controllers can be implemented with the flight computer throughput limitations. Note that these μ controllers used 2nd order (maximum) D-scales. If the D-scales were limited to 1st order, then the resulting controllers had between 62 and 90 states. Even though this state dimension is too large as well, it is interesting to note the significant difference in attenuation performance between the controllers with 1st and 2nd order D-scales. A comparison of attenuation performance for μ designs (with 2.5% uncertainty) is shown in Figure 9 which indicates that the lower order D-scales change the slope of the attenuation curve such that less attenuation is obtained above the break frequency. It appears to be preferable to use the higher order D-scales in conjunction with a fixed-order μ -synthesis design [9].

6. Conclusions

Previous approaches to microgravity vibration isolation system designs have utilized strictly classical methods with the exception of a few studies using H_2 and H_∞ methods. In this paper, H_2 and H_∞ methods have been shown to result in comparable levels of nominal performance, albeit at significantly different levels of robustness. An uncertainty model for microgravity vibration isolation controller design with respect to parametric uncertainties in umbilical stiffness and damping was used for robust stability analysis and robust

control design. μ -methods are shown to provide superior stability and performance robustness, although at the expense of high controller dimension. Future work will address fixed-order robust control designs based on the full-order D-scale information.

Figure 9: Affect of D-scale Order on Performance

References

1. Boeing Defense & Space Group Missiles and Space Division, "System Specification for the International Space Station," Specification #41000D, Nov. 1, 1995.
2. Grodsinsky, C. M., and Whorton, M. S., "A Survey of Active Vibration Isolation Systems for Microgravity Applications," Grodsinsky, C. M., and Whorton, M. S., *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, Vol. 37, No. 5, Sept.-Oct. 2000.
3. Hyde, T. T., "H₂ Synthesis for Active Vibration Isolation," American Controls Conference, Seattle, WA, June 1995.
4. Hampton, R. D. and Whorton, M. S., "Frequency-Weighting Filter Selection, for H₂ Control of Microgravity Isolation Systems: A Consideration of the 'Implicit Frequency Weighting' Problem," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, Vol. 49, No. 2, April 2000.
5. Fialho, I. J., "H-infinity control design for the active rack isolation system," Paper No. ACC00-IEEE0071, American Controls Conference, Chicago, IL, June 2000.
6. Whorton, M. S., "g-LIMIT: A Microgravity Vibration Isolation System for the International Space Station," AIAA-2001-5090, October 2001.
7. Balas, G., Doyle, J., Glover, K., Packard, A., and Smith, R., " μ -Analysis and Synthesis Toolbox."
8. Kim, Y. K., and Whorton, M. S., "Equations of Motion for the g-LIMIT Microgravity Vibration Isolation System," NASA TM-2001-211301, October 2001.
9. Whorton, M. S., Calise, A. J., and Hsu, C-C., "A Study of Fixed Order Mixed Norm Designs for a Benchmark Problem in Structural Control," *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*, No. 27, pp. 1315-1330, 1998